

Data	Source
Thermochronology data compilation (see also ADP3)	Blythe and Kleinspehn (1998); Dörr et al. (2012, 2019b, a), Schaaf et al. (2021), Japsen et al. (2023), Meier et al. (2024)
Svalbox: location of type section sedimentary logs, 360 images, 2D seismics, boreholes	http://portal.svalbox.no e.g., Senger et al. (2019, 2021), Betlem et al. (2023), Horota et al. (2024)
Research in Svalbard: geological fieldwork locations	https://researchinsvalbard.no/ see also ADP5
Geoscience Atlas maps (geology, paleogeography, resources, structural, geophysical etc.)	Digitized from Dallmann (2015)
Earthquake locations	Pirli et al. (2013), U.S. Geological Survey (2023)
Basemap and various geological maps	Norwegian Polar Institute https://geodata.npolar.no/ https://toposvalbard.npolar.no/
NGU gravity and magnetic compilations	Olesen et al. (2010)
Seismic refraction profile locations	Ritzmann and Jokat (2003), Ritzmann et al. (2004), Czuba et al. (2008), Aarseth et al. (2017)
Various geophysical data portals	BGR: https://arctic.bgr.de/mapapps4/resources/apps/arktis/index.html?lang=en AWI: https://maps.awi.de/awimaps/projects/public/?cu=geophysics_arctic#home NGU: https://geo.ngu.no/geoscienceportalopen/Results?bookmark=0bf79eb071474cd7a92240d4360b84db

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